

ON THE CONCEPTS OF "FORGIVENESS" IN UZBEKI AND ENGLISH
LANGUAGES PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract. The theory of phraseology was first founded by the French linguist S.Bally. Grammatical, semantic, functional and stylistic aspects of phraseologisms can also be seen in the researches of Russian linguists. For example, V. Vinogradov classifies expressions as a lexical layer according to meaning groups. Phraseologisms in Uzbek linguistics are widely studied in the works of scientists such as Sh.Rakhmatullaev, M.Sodikova, I.Kochkortoiev, A.Rafiev, B.Yoldoshev, A.Mamatov, Q.Hakimov, K.Bozorboev.

Keywords: emotionality, expressiveness, vocabulary unit, "excuse me", "I beg your pardon", "to err is human", let bygones be bygones.

**О ПОНЯТИЯХ «ПРОСТАНИЕ» В УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ
ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ЕДИНИЦЫ**

Аннотация: Теорию фразеологии впервые основал французский лингвист С.Балли. Грамматические, семантические, функциональные и стилистические аспекты фразеологизмов можно увидеть и в исследованиях российских лингвистов. Например, В. Виноградов классифицирует выражения как лексический пласт по смысловым группам. Фразеологизмы в узбекском языкознании широко изучаются в работах таких ученых, как Ш.Рахматуллаев, М.Содиқова, И.Кочқортоев, А.Рафиев, Б.Ёлдошев, А.Маматов, Г.Хақимов, К.Бозорбоев.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональность, экспрессивность, словарный запас, «извините», «прошу прощения», «человеку свойственно ошибаться», пусть прошлое останется в прошлом.

**O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDAGI “AFV ETISH” KONSEPTLARIDA
FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR**

Annotatsiya: Frazеologiya nazariyasiga dastlab fransuz tilshunosi Sh.Balli asos soldi . Frazеologizmlarning grammatik, semantik, funksional-uslubiy jihatlarini rus tilshunoslarining tadqiqotlarida ham ko‘rish mumkin. Masalan, V.Vinogradov iboralarni leksik qatlam sifatida ma‘no guruhlariga ko‘ra tasniflaydi . O‘zbek tilshunosligida frazeologizmlar Sh.Rahmatullaev, M.Sodiqova, I.Qo‘chqortoiev, A.Rafiev, B.Yo‘ldoshev, A.Mamatov, Q.Hakimov, K.Bozorboev kabi olimlar ishlarida keng o‘rganilgan .

Kalit so‘zlari: emotsionallik, ekspressivlik, lug'at birligi, "kechirasiz", "to err is human", let bygones be bygones.

The emergence and formation of phraseology is related to the figurative reflection of certain historical processes, social environment, life reality in Uzbek life and the ideas arising from it. During the formation period, phraseological units, like the lexicon, are subjected to the internal laws of each language, phonetic, lexical-grammatical requirements. They are used in an almost figurative sense and have the characteristics of emotionality and expressiveness by means of artistic images. Therefore, phraseology has a great impact not only on people's minds, but also on their emotions. Despite the fact that several words are included in the structure of phraseology,

they are united by a single common meaning and express an emotional-expressive meaning. Phraseologisms are used in fiction as a figurative and impressive tool.

A. Hajiyev in his "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" defines phraseological units as "structurally equivalent to a word combination, a sentence, semantically a whole, meaning a generalized meaning, not created in the speech process, but included ready for speech as a unit, a figurative type of stable compounds with a figurative meaning.

Professor Sh. Rahmatullayev recognizes as phraseological objects the lexical units consisting of two or more lexical bases, equivalent to a compound or sentence in terms of structure, alternative to a word in terms of content, and having a superlative meaning as a whole. Linguists such as B. Yoldoshev and A. Mamatov have a broad understanding of phraseologisms and research compound, static, figurative expressions as phraseologisms.

Phraseologisms are "stable linguistic units consisting of two or more components, the sum of their values is not equal." For example, the Russian phrase "спустя рукава" cannot be translated literally, but it should be understood that it is used in the sense of "poorly executed work". In particular, in English, the phraseological unit "to look forward" is used in the meaning of "waiting".

B.A. According to Larin, "only word combinations are included in the study of paremia and become the subject of phraseology. However, not every phrase is a phrase. ... As the simplest form of synthesizing expression, phrases are syntactically related speech units. But the sentences that depend on the semantic unity and semantic integrity of the internal structural combination of words cannot be the object of the study of syntax - they are very close to the lexeme, like mixed lexemes, they can be studied independently - in phraseology from the point of view of lexicology or in lexicography. should be reviewed.

The volume of phraseologisms and its main signs are directly connected, leading to the expansion of the scope of phraseologisms. Deterioration of characteristics characteristic of all phraseological units; increases the set of private properties and vice versa.

Characteristics of phraseological units;

- repetition of speech;
- stability (content, structure and semantics);
- value integrity;
- waterproofing;
- separate design of the component (superverbalism);
- accentological separate design;
- volatility;
- lexical meaning;
- component composition;
- grammatical categories;
- complete or partial desmantization of components;
- generality (common knowledge);
- idiomatic;
- equivalence or synonymy of words.

Among the phraseological units with the meaning "forgiveness" and "forgiveness" in English dictionaries are the following:

I'm sorry phrase

used for politely asking someone to repeat something that they have said pardon me phrase
mainly american used for politely asking someone to repeat something **excuse me phrase**
mainly american used for asking someone to repeat something
come again? phrase used for asking someone to repeat what they said what adverb
determiner interjection predeterminer pronoun spoken used for asking someone to repeat what
they have just said because you did not hear it clearly

I beg your pardon phrase

spoken formal used for asking someone to repeat something because you did not hear them.
“Pardon?” or “Sorry?” are less formal ways of saying this run that by me again phrasal verb spoken
used for asking someone to repeat what they have just said again adverb spoken used for asking
someone to repeat something that they told you before, especially because you have forgotten what
they said

you what? phrase

used for asking someone to repeat what they have just said. This is not a polite expression.
It is better to say pardon. back up phrasal verb mainly american used for telling someone to return
to something that was said earlier .

In the analysis of phraseology in the Uzbek language, the main focus is on the relevance
of the phraseology to the speech situation:

Aybga buyurmaysiz – You don't blame (used in the sense of forgiveness, apology for
some work, behavior). I said, "You don't blame me, let my son learn architecture and not become
a bricklayer like his father." Now, guests, don't blame me, I have a lot of work to do and a husband
to go to.

Aybga qo'shmaysiz - To commit a crime, to commit a guilty, shameful act. Don't do that,
people will blame\ (you will not blame). The maid set the table and brought food. As he placed a
bowl of soup in front of Samandarov, he said: "You don't blame me, brother Maqsudali, my aunt
made carrot soup."

To repent of one's sin, to repent of one's sin, to forgive one's sin - to forgive the person who
has committed a sin or wrongdoing. Did you become a boyfriend for the aunt? Remember that
your sin is over.

Aybiga ko'z yummoq – forgive a fault, forgive a mistake:

To get rid of a spoonful of blood - to forgive, pardon. To forgive one's sin, to avoid death,
to pardon. I'll tell you if you'll take a spoonful of my blood. - I'm gone, tell me. Forgive me, khagan,
our wayward servant, pass a spoonful of my blood. Liver (or tongue, liver, heart) blood Grief-
stricken, crushed with grief.

When looking at the English texts, in the dialogic texts, it is first used in the context of
apologizing and eliminating an awkward situation. In a similar situation, the following situation
can be seen: “I do not think we were speaking at all . Sir William could not have interrupted
any two people in the room who had less to say for themselves. We have tried two or three
subjects already without success, and what we are to talk of next I can not imagine”.
“What think you of books?” said he, smiling. “Books oh ! no. I am sure we never read
the same, or not with the same feelings”. “I am sorry you think so; but if that be
the case, there can at least be no want of subject. We may compare our different
opinions”. “No—I can not talk of books in a ball-room; my head is always full of
something else.”

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Formulas of thanks and apologies in the communicative mode are analyzed taking into account the factors that determine the choice of one or another level of politeness of the formulas of thanks.

Usually, the communicative situation plays an important role in the selection of vocabulary in Uzbek communication culture. Several factors influence the use of lexical items related to the concept of forgiveness.

In English, there is no phraseological unit that directly corresponds to the lexical unit "You will excuse me". However, the idioms "Excuse me", "I beg your, pardon" are very close in essence:

Phrase - excuse me

1. (Canada, US) Said as a request to repeat information.
2. (Canada, US) Said, as though as a request to repeat information, in order to indicate disbelief or indignation.
3. Said as a request for an individual's attention. quotations
4. Said as a request to pass somebody.
5. Sorry, as an apology.
6. (formal) Said as an expression of unexpected or early farewell .

Much of our private and public moral discourse takes place in apologizing, accepting, or demanding forgiveness, but we rarely make clear what we expect from a gesture of repentance. As a result, apologizing has become a vague, meaningless, and sometimes disgusting ritual. We intuitively understand that certain types of apologies can change the lives of both victims and offenders. However, some excuses can be worse than none at all. Sometimes empty gestures are like soul-searching apologies because it seems like the least onerous way to mend a relationship. In other cases, the offender may want to deliberately deceive or manipulate the victim into asking for forgiveness. Such hypocrisy occurs not only among enemies, but also among friends, relatives, and lovers. Whether an unrepentant leader instructs his lawyer to repent in order to settle a lawsuit, or an abusive husband who has no intention of reforming and tells his wife "sorry," we see him hurt.

Victims are more likely to be hurt if they give more meaning to an apology.

Please don't be mad at me. This is quite an informal phrase which we use when we've done something wrong and we don't want the other person to be angry with us. For example: "Please don't be mad at me but I have to cancel our plans this weekend".

1	Excuse me	Kechirasiz
2	Ever so sorry.	Har doim kechirasiz.
3	How stupid/careless/thoughtless of me.	Qanday ahmoq / beparvo / men haqimda.
4	I apologize.	Meni ma'zur tuting.
5	I had that wrong.	Menda xato bor edi.
6	I hope you can forgive me.	Umid qilamanki, siz meni kechira olasiz.
7	I owe you an apology.	Men sizdan kechirim so'rashga majburman.
8	I sincerely apologize.	Men chin dildan kechirim so'rayman.

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9	I take full responsibility.	Men to'liq javobgarlikni o'z zimmamga olaman.
10	I want to apologize.	Men kechirim so'ramoqchiman.
11	I wanted to tell you I'm sorry.	Men sizga kechirim so'raganimni aytmoqchi edim.
12	I was wrong about that.	Men bu haqda xato qilganman.
13	I'd like to apologize.	Men kechirim so'ramoqchiman.
14	I'd like to apologize for how I reacted esterday.	Kechagi munosabatim uchun uzr so'ramoqchiman.
15	I'm (so/very/terribly) sorry.	Men (juda/juda/dahshatli) afsusdaman.
16	My apologies.	Uzr so'rayman.
17	My fault, bro (US)	Mening aybim, uka (AQSh)
18	Oh, my bad.	Oh, mening yomonligim.
19	Pardon (me)	
20	Please accept our (sincerest) apologies.	Kechirasiz (men)
21	Please don't be mad at me.	Iltimos, bizning (samimiy) uzrimizni qabul qiling.
22	Please excuse my (ignorance)	

Robert Allen's Dictionary of English Phraseologisms focuses on idioms rather than idioms. The classification of phraseological units proposed by Robert Allen can be summarized as follows:

Phrases according to form: idiom, collocation, quasi, idioms;

According to the content: phrases, paremias.

The reason for our classification in this way is that idioms, collocations and quasi-idioms differ from each other in terms of their formal structure. For example, units called collocation mean that certain verbs are combined with some prepositions and mean an additional meaning other than the basic meaning. In terms of content, paremias and phrasemes differ from each other. It can be seen in the examples of proverbs, articles, expressions analyzed above.

Bygone let bygones be bygones (O'tgan ishga salovat)

to forgive past offences - Bygone is a Middle English word, recorded first as an adjective in the meaning 'that has passed' (with reference to time). This is the meaning in Hermione's words at the beginning of Shakespeare's *The Winter's Tale* This satisfaction - The bygone day proclaimed. The phrase is 17th cent. in its current form .

Somerset Maugham *The Moon and Sixpence* 1919 I want him to come back. If he'll do that. we'll let bygones be bygones. After all, we've been married for seventeen ears.

According to the contextual meaning of this phrase, it means to forgive the mistake made before and to forget this mistake.

let bygones be bygones (O'tgan ishga salovat)

phrase - used to tell someone that they should forget about unpleasant things that happened in the past, and especially to forgive and forget something bad that someone has done to them .

Just let bygones be bygones and be friends again.

Why can't you let bygones be bygones and put it all behind you?

My mother thinks I should let bygones be bygones but I'm struggling with it.

After all these years, surely it's time to let bygones be bygones.

If she's willing, I'm willing to let bygones be bygones.

“to err is human” (Hamma xato qiladi/ beayb parvardigor) a justification for human error: in full to err is human, to forgive divine. The locus classicus in English is Alexander Pope’s Essay on Criticism, line: ‘Good nature and good sense must ever join; | To err is human; to forgive, divine.’ However, the phrase, and certainly the sentiment, are a lot older, and can be found in Chaucer and further back in Latin (humanum est errare). In the Roman dramatist Plautus the maxim appears in the form humanum amare est, humanum autem ignoscere est (Mercator II.ii.48 ‘It is human to love, and human also to forgive’).

Uzbek language phrases were created based on the rules of Islam. Most of the religious expressions in the Uzbek language are influenced by Arabic and Persian languages, and it should be mentioned that the religious phrases in the English language are copied from the Latin language.

Although the fund of language paremies from the point of view of linguistics is mainly limited to phraseological units, proverbs and sayings, in fact their scope is wide.

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